

Ariadne: User-Centered Music Discovery in a Labyrinth of Semantic Threads

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"Talking about music is like dancing about architecture."
–Martin Mull

To my parents and my sister.

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Abstract

The last two decades have seen continued increases in the amount of music that is readily accessible online, the variety of devices through which we can access it, and the speed at which we do so. Despite this growth, our means of interaction with large music catalogs remain the same, predominated by search-driven and text-based interfaces that limit their potential explorability. We aim to develop an interface to browse music collections that overcomes these limitations.

We achieve this following a user-centered approach: by means of in-depth interviews with music listeners, we link certain user profiles with specific unmet interaction needs that, once met, make exploratory browsing possible. The interviews reveal that a certain type of users find existing platforms for music discovery to be opaque, obscuring both control over the exploration and information about the new music behind black-box algorithms.

To overcome this opacity we present *Ariadne*, an open-source web interface that exposes the MusicBrainz catalog. It allows users to browse a music catalog as a growing map of connected dots that represent songs and the explicit semantic relationships between them. By at the same time shaping and exploring this music space in an interactive way, users can discover new music while learning about it and how it is related to music they already know.

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Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Why do we need new music?

This is one of the seemingly innocent questions that have been my entry point to the study of the beautifully complex construct that is our experience of music. We are all familiar with the thrill of finding new music that speaks to us, and yet where exactly that feeling comes from remains elusive.

Over the course of this project, I have had the chance to deal with questions like this by diving into inspiring literature in fields ranging from cognition and the philosophy of science to musicology and human-computer interaction; but also by getting to know first-hand the habits and needs of real people when they listen to music. Interestingly, both well-established authors and in-the-wild experience with music listeners point in similar directions: they both suggest that there is an intuitive, irrational, or "hard to explain" component to our drive towards discovery.

I would like to introduce this work by presenting one of the answers to this question that I came across in my literature review. It has been suggested that we listen to music to regulate our mood, to achieve or increase self-awareness, and as an expression of our social relatedness [1]. As time goes by, we link certain music to certain stages of our life [2], and so the changes we experience in our personality, self-image, and social reality come hand in hand with a need for new music to which we can relate new situations.

For those of us born in the years and countries close to the burst of information technology, this has particularly interesting implications. At a point in our lives when we our

personality, self-image, and social reality were making their first baby steps, the way we experienced music changed in the blink of an eye. The experience of music that implied listening to the radio and buying what we liked on CD –both of them technologies that also changed music forever– lasted little time. From quite early on in our lives, we’ve been used to having vast amounts of music only a few clicks away, often in our own pockets and at zero cost.

That music plays an important role in our lives, and especially in our youth, is not news by any means [2]. However, young and future generations’ experience of music differs significantly from that of previous ones in one critical aspect: the challenges we face when we look for new music. For the first time in human history, the main difficulty we face in finding new music –or any other kind of information, for that matter– is not the lack of it, but its overabundance. Listening to an artist that a friend recommends us, finding out the name of a song that’s playing in a bar, or discovering a band from another continent, tasks that could be long or even impossible a few decades ago, are now so easy that we don’t even think of them as problems.

On the other hand, we now face the problem of the overabundance of music. Ubiquitous streaming is well on its way to make possessing music unnecessary. What to listen to next, if it could be anything? Online music catalogs are increasing at overwhelming rates, with Spotify adding over 40 days of music to their catalog every day [3]. What to listen to next, if there is more music online than we will ever be able to listen to?

Despite these increases in the size of online music catalogs in the past two decades, our means of accessing them have hardly changed. We are often limited to writing text in search boxes and getting results in the form of a list. These interfaces are highly useful when we want to retrieve a certain item we already know from the catalog. When it comes to discovering new music, however, the main premise is that we don’t know what we are looking for. We therefore face the challenge of developing technology that enables our human need for new music to be met in the age of information overabundance. Furthermore, given the human need underlying the technological challenge, we believe that any improvement should build upon an understanding of users’ habits and needs, and the problems they face when using existing solutions.

In this thesis, we intend to answer the following question:

How can specific problems that users face when finding new music be solved through alternative ways of browsing music catalogs?

The work dedicated to answering it is presented in the remainder of this document, which is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 presents a review of existing work related to music discovery.
- Chapters 3 and 4 introduces the methodology used in the development of the proposed solution. The user-centered approach used to identify the target problem and audience is presented in Chapter 3, while the specifics of the implementation of the proposed solution are covered in Chapter 4.
- Chapter 5 provides concluding remarks and directions for future work.

Chapter 2

STATE OF THE ART

This chapter presents a review of existing work related to music discovery. Its aim is twofold: first, to root the development of the project at hand in broader ground by drawing upon existing knowledge in the fields of philosophy, cognition, human-computer interaction, and information visualization. Secondly, to provide a comprehensive and multifaceted study of existing approaches to music discovery, so as to draw knowledge and inspiration, and identify the gaps on which this work will focus.

It is structured as follows: Section 2.1 introduces the concept of discovery at a general level, and states the relevance and technological implications of its study in the digital age. Next, in Section 2.2, these concepts are applied to music discovery in particular, explaining why and how technology nowadays plays a key role in finding new music. A wealth of existing approaches to music discovery are reviewed in Section 2.3. Finally, Section 2.4 concludes the chapter and presents the research gaps identified in the review.

2.1 Discovery

2.1.1 What is discovery?

The Oxford English Dictionary defines the verb *to discover* as "to find accidentally or during a search" [4]. Within this definition, however, a few distinctions are made. To discover can mean "to be the first to find or observe something", like when we talk about the discovery of penicillin, but also "to become aware of a fact" –for example, someone discovering that their

lover has an affair. To discover can also mean "to show interest in an activity or subject for the first time", like a teenager that discovers poetry, or even "to be the first to recognize the potential of a performer", as in rapper Usher's discovery of Justin Bieber. To obtain a general understanding of what discovery is, we will study in detail the first two of these specific definitions.

The first definition –observing or finding something for the first time– describes an essential part of science in both its goal –generating new knowledge– and methodology –finding new evidence. In this sense, scientific discovery has long been studied from an epistemological point of view. Indeed, one of the most relevant works in contemporary epistemology is titled *The Logic of Scientific Discovery* [5], in which Karl Popper aims to provide a logical analysis of the procedure by which we generate new knowledge. However, Popper acknowledges that there is an irrational component to the initial stage of conceiving an idea, that "neither calls for logical analysis nor is susceptible of it". This distinction between the irrational or lucky and the logical or methodical components of science is similar to Reichenbach's [6] idea of the two distinct scientific contexts of discovery and justification, the former being characterized by probabilistic induction and the latter by logical analysis. In this sense, Gigerenzer [7] proposes a middle ground for the study of scientific discovery, suggesting a heuristics of discovery "less general than a supposed unique logic [...] but more general than lucky guess". Furthermore, Gigerenzer criticizes philosophers', logicians' and mathematicians' focus on the context of justification and their dismissal of the context of discovery as something unworthy of scientific interest. In short, from the perspective of the philosophy of science, discovery is the process of arriving at new valid knowledge, and implies both a logical methodology and an element of uncertainty that can be termed as lucky, probabilistic, serendipitous, or chaotic.

The second of the definitions provided above –becoming aware of a fact–, is not concerned with generating knowledge *for the first time*, as science is. It is rather concerned with the process by which an individual can gain knowledge previously unknown *to them*, and therefore lies within the field of cognition. Jerome Bruner [8] defines this type of discovery as "rearranging or transforming evidence in such a way that one is enabled to go beyond the evidence [...] to additional new insights", and stresses the importance of preparation and

predisposition in discovery: "discovery, like surprise, favors the well-prepared mind". From this point of view, discovery is the cognitive process of arriving at new knowledge through new evidence and/or a perspective shift of existing evidence, and is therefore more likely to happen in the presence of abundant existing knowledge.

2.1.2 Why is discovery relevant?

The benefits of discovery

In a 1961 article, Jerome Bruner [8] wrote about the relevance of discovery as a pedagogical tool, stressing the importance and benefits of letting students work things out on their own, or, as Bruner puts it, to "be their own discoverer". For Bruner, teaching can be done in *hypothetical mode* –in which the student and teacher cooperate, and the student plays an active role in the formulation of ideas– or in *expository mode* –in which the exposition of ideas is entirely determined by the teacher and the student merely listens. According to Bruner, there are four potential benefits for the student that are derived from learning through discovery in hypothetical mode:

- An increase in intellectual potency as a result of the practice of formulating and testing hypotheses.
- A shift in the student's motivations: from extrinsic pressures for success, "giving back", or "doing the right thing", to an intrinsic search for growth and knowledge in which success and failure are no longer reward and punishment but merely information.
- Learning the heuristics of inquiry and discovery, which Bruner states can only be achieved by further engaging in inquiry and discovery.
- An improvement in memory capabilities, as information is better stored and organized when done so with the intention of being actively used later rather than when received solely for storage.

Besides these pedagogical benefits, discovery is claimed to induce a feeling of *cognitive pleasure* in the discoverer [9], an effect also experienced, for example, when solving chal-

lenges, exploring new territory or learning something new about oneself. The main premise behind cognitive pleasure theory is that pleasure can be taken through cognitive engagement with an activity. This has recently drawn the attention of some working in the field of user experience (UX) design [10], who take it as an argument in favor of rethinking the trend in UX to make everything as easy as possible for the user. In this view, unnecessary complexity should indeed be avoided, but one should also consider the fact that the user will develop a higher engagement with a system if there is some cognitive effort involved in the interaction with it.

The need for discovery technology

With the ubiquity of Internet access, we now sit only a few keystrokes, finger taps, or voice commands away from more information than ever before in human history. We are able to access more information, faster, in a richer variety of formats, and through a wider range of devices and means of interaction.

However, this isn't necessarily good news. As E. O. Wilson put it, "we are drowning in information, while starving for wisdom" [11]. This implies a distinction between information and knowledge: to achieve wisdom, one needs more than a lot of data –Wilson goes as far as to suggest that we have too much of it. Herbert A. Simon approaches the matter from an attention-economic point of view: "Information [...] consumes the attention of its recipients. Hence a wealth of information creates a poverty of attention and a need to allocate that attention efficiently among the overabundance of information sources that might consume it" [12]. Drawing from these ideas, in his 2007 book *Information Foraging Theory: Adaptive Interaction With Information* [13], Peter Pirolli claims that, in the Information Age, the main challenge has shifted from collecting information to increasing the rate at which people access useful and valuable information, and stresses the relevance of the emerging research field of Human-Information Interaction.

And we are nowhere near solving this problem. In fact, one could argue that things are worse off nowadays than when Wilson's book *Consilience: The Unity of Knowledge*, containing the above quote, was published in 1999. Back then, the Internet was home to approximately 3 million unique hostnames [14], and had roughly 250 million unique users, which accounted

for about 5% of the world population [15]. In 2015, the Internet had more than 850 million unique hostnames [14] and 3.3 billion unique users –46% of the world population [15]. A 2016 report by IBM [16] claimed that 90% of the data existing at that time was created within the previous two years.

Despite these sustained increases in the volumes of data available, of users producing and consuming it, and of websites, applications, and services through which we can access it, there has been little progress towards preventing us from drowning in it, as Wilson would put it. Indeed, more than two decades after the dawn of the search engine, the ways we search for information online have not improved significantly: we type text into a box and get results in the form of a ranked list. Dörk et al. [17] claim this prevalence of text- and list-based interfaces limits the way we understand *information spaces* –frameworks that place information elements in a conceptual space according to certain principles, so that orientation and navigation become possible. Building on the analogy of how the vision of a flat Earth constrained people’s perception of the world, they introduce the concept of *textual flattening* as the transformation of "multifarious information spaces into flat worlds of text" as a result of the current primacy of text as a means of accessing information.

One might ask what is wrong with text-based queries and lists of results. Indeed, whether we want to know the ancestry of a certain English footballer or a ranking of the most visited cities in the world, typing a few words into a search box gets us the information we need almost instantly. However, this Oracle-like paradigm in which one gets the right answer by asking the right question does not support more exploratory forms of information-seeking [17]. Text-based search engines and lists of results make finding something specific very easy, but what if we don’t know what we are looking for? Current technology does not support browsing clothes on an online store the way we would walk through them in a physical store, or digging through crates of vinyls in a record shop, or simply walking around an unknown city to get a feel for its people and landscape. We therefore face the technological challenge of developing new means of accessing and browsing information that support exploratory browsing rather than explicit question-answering.

2.1.3 How do we embed discovery in technology?

Building on the needs stated above, Dörk et al [17] propose explorability as a design principle for information-seeking interfaces, emphasizing overview and orientation as key concepts that can turn abstract information spaces into graspable information landscapes. This implies, they assert, presenting data items in a way that allows their user to holistically understand the broader context of their collection, often through interactive visualizations of higher complexity than list-based interfaces. They mention computational semantics, interactive web graphics, and touch-enabled devices as emergent technologies (as of 2011) that can help pave the way for interfaces that make large information spaces intellectually and practically accessible.

Similarly, Peuquet et al. [18], in a 2002 paper, propose the use of maps as a powerful tool for the visualization of data containing spatial information. This idea is all the more relevant nowadays, with millions of tweets, news articles, blog posts, Facebook status updates and many other types of information featuring location data being generated at outstanding rates. Peuquet and her colleague suggest thinking of maps not as a final product, but as a medium for the exploration of data through its geographical distribution. They also present, building on cognitive literature, a set of properties in images and visualizations that promote insight and discovery:

- **Novelty:** Presenting the image in an unusual way: changing the size, orientation, or color of some of the elements.
- **Incongruity:** Adding elements that are usually not seen in the same image, such as lines indicating temporal evolution over a static map, i.e. combining space and time into a single image.
- **Ambiguity:** Presenting an image that can be interpreted in more than one way.
- **Abstraction:** Removing the detail in a certain aspect of an image, e.g. painting all of the sea the same shade of blue on a map.

2.2 Music Discovery

In the previous section we reviewed the meaning of discovery and the benefits, needs, and means for its technological study in the digital age. In this section, we will apply these concepts to music. What does it mean to discover music? How do we benefit from finding new music? Why is there a need for technology that helps us find new music? How should this technology work?

2.2.1 What is music discovery?

Simply put, music discovery is the process of finding new music. However, as it was the case in Section 2.1.1, we can make a few distinctions: music discovery can simply mean keeping up with new music, "new" roughly meaning "recently released" in this sense; but it can also mean finding "new old" music that we don't know, "new" meaning "previously unknown" in this context. Following the other definitions of discovery given in Section 2.1.1, to discover music can also mean showing interest in a genre or generation of artists for the first time (as in *discovering Hip-Hop*), or to be the first to recognize the potential of an artist.

2.2.2 Why is music discovery relevant?

The benefits of discovering music

Schäfer et al. [1] suggest that we listen to music mainly to regulate arousal and mood, to increase or achieve self-awareness, and as an expression of social relatedness. Over time, as our personality, self-image, and social environment evolve, we begin to link certain music to certain memories or stages of our life [2], and it is fair to assume that we will have an interest in finding new music that will reflect our current situation. Thus, whichever of the previous definitions of music discovery we might choose, the most important and immediate benefit of discovering music is clear: the new music itself.

However, when we find new music it is usually accompanied by a wealth of information about it and the situation in which we encountered it: typically, the artist that wrote or performed it, the name and release date of the album that includes it, and its genre, but

potentially also the name and musical preferences of whoever recommended it to us, the look and feel of the place where we heard it playing and the other people who were there, other artists performing in the same festival, other songs featured in the same film... All this information is used to put the new music in context, in the extremely complex construct that is our personal experience of music. Indeed, Laplante et al. [19] recognize the acquisition of information *about* music as the second main outcome of music-seeking (the first one being, as stated above, the new music itself). This information, they claim, is gathered in order to enrich the listening experience, to increase the listener's musical knowledge, and to improve the way music will be found in the future. Similarly, Lillie [20] mentions challenging our assumptions about music and expanding the ways in which we represent it as one of the goals of music discovery.

Besides these *utilitarian* outcomes of music discovery, Laplante et al. [19] mention *hedonic* outcomes as being an important part of the music-seeking experience. These hedonic outcomes include pleasure, fun, a feeling of absorption, or a lack of awareness of physical surroundings. This links to the ideas of cognitive pleasure presented in Section 2.1.2: finding something new, exploring new territory, or learning something are ways of engaging cognitively in an activity, and thus we feel pleasure in succeeding in them.

The need for technology in music discovery

A 2014 article in The Guardian [21] explored the future of music discovery at Spotify with the development of highly accurate and personalized recommendation engines. The comments section, however, consisted almost exclusively of strongly worded opinions against the development of high-tech solutions to a problem that we can solve quite successfully without hardly any technology. After all, music was around –and was being discovered– long before high-quality streaming and recommendation algorithms. Another 2014 article in The Guardian [22] listed "the five types of music discovery": algorithms made it on the list only as a "not awe-inspiring" yet "improving" way of finding new music, while friends, curators, crowds, and serendipity were also mentioned as equally valid alternatives. Why should we need technology to find new music?

This question can be answered following the reasons for the development of information discovery technology presented in Section 2.1.2. Before the digital age, the main challenge in finding music was the lack of information: one had to resort to friends, radio curators, record shop experts, and bars, clubs, and festivals to find new music. Nowadays, tens of millions of songs sit a few clicks away. This wealth of information creates, as Herbert A. Simon would put it, a poverty of attention [12]: what to listen to next, if it could be anything? The main challenge now, as pointed out by Pirolli [13], is improving the way we access information so that we get as much useful and valuable information as possible, with a minimal waste of time.

Continuing on the parallel with Section 2.1.2, we can see that music information spaces have suffered from the same *textual flattening* that Dörk et al. criticize [17]. While browsing CD's in a record store, there are many subtle cues that guide us through the catalog and help us find new music: we might find an unknown album that is alphabetically placed next to our favorite artist in the shelf containing a genre we like; the artwork, typography, and design convey cultural messages that shape our decisions; the overall musical atmosphere of the store further engages us in our search. Many of these subtleties are lost in the flat and homogeneous search-driven text-based interfaces we use to access music online. However, these interfaces are the present and future of music access, in the same way that computers are the present and future of access to information. As long as our music is online, we face the challenge of developing more efficient and explorable ways of accessing it.

Finally, it is worth noting that technology is not incompatible with other forms of music discovery, nor should it aim to replace them. Instead, the role of technology is to develop tools that improve and complement the way we do things. As Section 2.3 will show, a vast range of tools have been proposed that improve the traditional ways of finding new music stated above: friends, crowds, curators, and serendipity. Collaborative playlists, live streams with built-in chatrooms, artist-made playlists, and real-time song identification in noisy environments are just a few examples of the way technology can let us do what we have always done in ways that would otherwise be impossible.

2.2.3 How do we embed music discovery in technology?

In Section 2.1.3 we saw that explorability has recently been suggested as a design principle for information-seeking interfaces [17]. Along this line, Laplante et al. [19] suggest designing music browsing interfaces in a way that allows users to explore the collection without having a specific query in mind. They found that users generally have very vague and ill-defined goals in mind when searching for music, and call for interfaces to be designed with this fact in mind. The automatic playback of related songs is suggested in order to promote surprise and serendipitous discovery, which could be seen as the natural evolution of a random scanning of the dial on a radio, or the random shuffling of songs on an mp3 player. The authors also suggest providing the user with a richer variety of metadata and related content in order to fulfill their need for information *about* music.

The search for alternatives to list-based interfaces has led to a growing number of experimental visualizations of music catalogs, the most relevant of which are covered in Section 2.3. In some of these cases, the specifications of complex algorithms that generate the visualizations are adapted so as to include key aspects of the music discovery user experience: Collares et al. [23], for example, modified an algorithm that places songs in a 2D map according to their audio similarity so that the user could specify the location of a set of *anchor* songs, which were placed randomly in the original version of the algorithm. This is an illustrative example of how users' information browsing needs (in this case, the need for reference points and orientation) can be translated into specific and effective design solutions.

2.3 Existing Platforms for Music Discovery

The previous section presented the main challenges and opportunities brought to music discovery by the digital age. To deal with them, both industry and academia have devoted substantial efforts to the development of platforms intended to provide users with new music in a wide variety of ways. In this section, we review the most relevant contributions to music discovery according to four aspects:

- a) The amount of user interaction they imply.

- b) The device for which they are developed.
- c) The technologies on which they rely.
- d) The aspect on which they focus.

This review is summarized at the end of the chapter in Table 2.1

2.3.1 Music discovery systems by level of interaction

This section introduces various music discovery platforms according to the amount of user interaction they require. As we will see, music discovery platforms range from minimal radio-like apps that stream an expert-curated playlist to the user's pocket; all the way to full-screen desktop environments that engage the user in active and complex explorations.

Online music radio

On the low-interaction side of this spectrum is online music radio [24]: platforms that require as little user input as opening the platform and selecting a stream of music from a predefined list. In platforms such as SHOUTcast¹, music is streamed in a broadcast-like way, so that all users are simultaneously listening to the same track. In other situations, the ability to skip or repeat songs is allowed but limited, even for paying users. This is the case of Nokia MixRadio² –discontinued in 2016– and Pandora³ –as of 2017, only available in the United States, Australia and New Zealand.

Music recommendation

On a slightly higher level of interaction is music recommendation [25], used by platforms to passively build models of their users' preferences as they listen to music in order to suggest new items they might like. It naturally requires the use of the platform over a certain period of time in order to accurately model a user's taste. A landmark example of music recommendation is Spotify⁴ Discover Weekly, a service that provides a playlist that is updated weekly

¹<https://www.shoutcast.com>

²<http://www.mixradiomusic.com>

³<http://www.pandora.com>

⁴<http://www.spotify.com>

tailored to each individual user's taste, and that reached 10 billion plays only 10 weeks after being released [26]. Many other platforms also provide users with personalized suggestions based on the taste they express, either implicitly through listening and skipping, or explicitly by liking, saving, and sharing (see Figure 2.1). These platforms include Apple Music⁵, Last.fm⁶, SoundCloud⁷, Pandora⁸, Deezer⁹, Google Play Music¹⁰, Amazon Prime Music¹¹, and many more.

Figure 2.1: Music recommendation on SoundCloud based on implicit (listening) and explicit (liking) taste.

Playlist generation

At a similar level of interaction is playlist generation [27]. The aim of this task is to provide the user with a list of songs similar to a *seed set*, which can be a song, an album, an artist, or another playlist. A well known example is Apple iTunes' Genius [28], a service that provides users of the iTunes media library and music store software with new songs from the online catalog that are similar to a seed set from the user's personal collection. This service is now integrated in the Apple Music streaming platform, which also offers the ability to create on-the-fly *radios* with music similar to a seed set. Spotify¹² offers a very similar service (see Figure

⁵<http://www.apple.com/music>

⁶<http://www.last.fm>

⁷<http://www.soundcloud.com>

⁸<http://www.pandora.com>

⁹<http://www.deezer.com>

¹⁰<https://play.google.com/music/listen>

¹¹<https://music.amazon.com>

¹²<http://www.spotify.com>

2.2), also termed *radio*, in a use of the word that is notably different from that introduced in Section 2.3.1. In a similar application, Germain et al. [29] propose the generation of a Spotify playlist from the user’s listening history and Facebook likes on artist pages. Sandvold et al. [30] propose the use of a personalized auto-tagging system based on music similarity to generate playlists, in the form factor of a plugin for the now discontinued Winamp music player¹³. YouTube¹⁴, although strictly speaking not a music discovery platform, hosts a wide and unstructured variety of music. Its Related Mix feature, which automatically generates a list of videos related to a seed video chosen by the user, is commonly used as a music playlist generator.

Figure 2.2: Spotify song radio for *The Guns Of Brixton*, by The Clash.

Music exploration

Finally, on the high-interaction end of this spectrum is the task known as music exploration [31], which aims to improve the way large music catalogs are browsed by going beyond simple list-based interfaces. Elias Pampalk’s Islands of Music [32] [33] (see Figure 2.3) and the subsequent interfaces it inspired [31] [34] (see Figure 2.4) are often cited examples of such interfaces, using 2D maps and 3D worlds as metaphors in which similar songs are placed together. Other metaphors include circles in abstract 2D planes, in which distance and color

¹³<http://www.winamp.com>

¹⁴<http://www.youtube.com>

represent music similarity and genre respectively [20] (see Figure 2.5); galaxies in a music similarity space [35]; or rainbows in which different colors represent different genres, and similar songs within a genre are placed close together [36].

As its name suggests, music exploration aims at building an active exploratory relationship between the user and the music collection, enabling them not only to discover new music but also to learn –or challenge their previous assumptions [20]– about the relationships between different types of music. This naturally implies a high level of user interaction.

Figure 2.3: Screenshot of Elias Pampalk's Islands of Music [32].

Although commonly used in the literature, the term *music exploration* remains somewhat ambiguous, and the difference between *exploration* and *discovery* remains unclear. From this point on, we will use the term *active music exploration* to refer to both a) the active and attentive browsing of a music collection with the goal of finding new songs, and learning about them and how they are related, and b) the research field concerned with the development of new interfaces that make this type of browsing possible.

2.3.2 Music discovery systems by device

The device for which different music discovery platforms are developed depends greatly on the type of service and experience they provide. On one hand, versatile music platforms [24] such as Apple Music [37] or Spotify [38], which offer vast catalogs in the tens of millions, and provide a wide range of features from online radio and playlist generation to mood- or context-based browsing and social media integration, aim to be users' first choice in any environment, and therefore offer fully-fledged applications for desktop, mobile and tablet devices.

Discovery platforms requiring less user input, as discussed in Section 2.3.1, are better suited for mobile use than others that imply more complex interactions. Nokia MixRadio, as well as several prototypes developed for Nokia by Lehtiniemi [24], are built specifically for mobile devices. Furthermore, Lehtiniemi proposes the use of location data to provide context-specific music discovery, taking advantage of the small dimensions of mobile devices and turning what could seem to be a drawback in terms of interactive capabilities into a differentiating strength of his approach.

On the other hand, active music exploration platforms, as they require a considerable amount of user interaction, are better suited for environments in which the user does not need to pay attention to external events and can focus entirely on the interaction, the exploration experience, and the music. All of the active music exploration platforms studied in this review except for those presented by Lehtiniemi [24] were developed as desktop applications.

2.3.3 Music discovery systems by technology used

As we have seen in the previous sections, many different ways of providing users with new music have been proposed throughout the years. Behind this variety of experiences, naturally, lies an equally diverse set of technologies, the most relevant of which are presented in this section.

Technology and differentiation

By automating the process of finding the *best new music* from vast collections, technology sits at the foundation of any music discovery platform, and therefore many music discovery services are highly differentiated by the technology they use. Shazam¹⁵ uses its signature audio fingerprinting algorithm [39] to automatically identify what song is playing, and provides the user with recommendations and links to buy the song on online stores, save it on music platforms, or share it on social media. Pandora uses large amounts of expert-annotated data to generate recommendations based on highly accurate high-level descriptions of the music. Beats Music, which would later be absorbed by Apple Music, offered a large amount of playlists crafted by curators who are well known in the industry: producers, editors of music magazines, organizers of music festivals, radio presenters, or even other artists and DJs.

Collaborative filtering

Collaborative filtering has been the prevailing approach to music recommendation for many years [40], assuming that if individuals I_1 and I_2 like songs S_1 and S_2 , and I_1 also likes S_3 , then I_2 is more likely to enjoy S_3 than a randomly chosen person. However, it introduces what is known as the *cold start* problem [40]: it is impossible to recommend items for which the system still does not have user ratings. This means that, of all new items, only those which are popular will get ratings and thus get recommended, while unknown new songs are never rated and thus remain unknown as they are never recommended. This cycle reinforces the *long tail* distribution of popularity in music catalogs, with the top 1% of songs receiving over 80% of plays [41].

¹⁵<https://www.shazam.com>

Content-based music recommendation

To overcome these issues, content-based music recommendation [40] aims at generating suggestions based exclusively on the music data (i.e. audio) and metadata (e.g. artist, album or genre tags). By focusing on the *content* rather than the *context*, which is unavailable in the cold start problem, new items can be recommended without the need for previous ratings. This makes popularity-independent recommendation possible.

Music similarity

At the core of music discovery is the idea of providing users with music that is both new and likely to be enjoyed by them. In order to ensure the latter, a common and reasonable assumption is that users are likely to enjoy music that is similar to other music they like. This has led to the development of the research field of music similarity, the goal of which is to automatically measure the degree to which two music recordings are similar [42].

This naturally poses several challenges, as highlighted by Berenzweig [42]:

- **Inter-Individual Variation:** Our perception of music possesses complex physiological, neurological, psychological, and cultural dimensions [43]. That different people have different tastes and opinions is inherent to human nature, and thus it is difficult to establish a universal and objective criterion for music similarity.
- **Intra-Individual Variation:** Personal musical tastes and opinions also change over time as a natural result of life experience. As Berenzweig points out, we tend to label music that holds no interest for us as "sounding the same". Therefore, as our interests change, so does our inner notion of similarity.
- **Multi-dimensionality:** Music can be similar or different in virtually any aspect that can be attributed to it [44]: instrumentation, rhythm, melody, mood, genre, cultural background...
- **Non-metricity:** Perceived similarity violates the properties of symmetry and triangle inequality [45], which are necessary for the definition of a metric in the Euclidean sense.

Nevertheless, several approaches to the computational measurement of music similarity have been proposed with promising results. Bogdanov [46] proposes the combination of low-level timbre, rhythm, harmony, and metadata features with high-level mood tags that are inferred by a previously trained classifier. The approach proposed by Seyerlehner et al. [47] obtained the best results in the MIREX music similarity evaluation challenge [48] in 2010, 2012, 2013, and 2014. It uses a set of handcrafted block-level features, which sit at an intermediate aggregation level between the frame and the song levels, that measure aspects of the signal spectrum such as contrast, fluctuation, and correlation. Genre tags are estimated from these features, and both the tags and the features are used in the final similarity estimation.

Dimensionality reduction

In the field of active music exploration, the development of non-list-based interfaces often revolves around the definition of 2D or 3D metaphor spaces that represent music similarity. As explained previously, it is difficult to establish absolute and linear dimensions of music similarity, let alone reduce these to two or three. Most approaches therefore rely on performing some kind of dimensionality reduction on a high-dimensional space comprised of features describing musically meaningful facets such as rhythm, melody, harmony, timbre or metadata e.g. artist, genre, mood...

Pampalk [32] [33], Schedl et al. [31], Knees et al. [34], and Jentsch [49] rely on the self-organizing map, also known as Kohonen map [50], a particular type of neural network that places similar high-dimensional items together in a low-dimensional grid through an unsupervised learning process. Lillie [20] uses a standard principal component analysis (PCA) [51] to identify the linear subspace projection of the high-dimensional space that maximizes variance, i.e. maximizing the spread of the points in the 2D plane. Lamere [52] and Stober [35] use landmark-based multidimensional scaling (LMDS) [53], a technique similar to PCA based on identifying landmark data points. Finally, Soriano et al. use least squares projection [54], finding a subspace projection that minimizes the squared error between the original points and their projections.

2.3.4 Music discovery systems by area of focus

In this section we consider the disciplines and fields from which different music discovery platforms have been proposed. The development of these interfaces is by nature interdisciplinary, as it requires knowledge about music, its computational analysis, and various aspects of design such as interface and user-centered design. Therefore, contributions to music discovery from the academic world usually stem from research in either algorithms or design.

The interfaces proposed by Schedl et al. [31], Pampalk [32] [33] [36], Lillie [20], Stober [35], and Soriano et al. [55] are examples of algorithm-centered research in music discovery. Although the research questions the authors pose are indeed related to the end-user browsing experience, and they often conduct subjective evaluations, the interface concepts they start from are not questioned throughout their development, and the research is instead focused on building technology that makes the interfaces possible.

On the other hand, Lehtiniemi [24], Jentsch [49], Arhippainen et al. [56], Chen [57], and Hoashi et al. [58] are examples of research in music discovery that is focused on interface, interaction, and user-centered design. In these cases, the research questions are concerned with identifying the traits and needs that relate users and discovery services [56], the aspects of the interaction that critically impact the browsing experience [57], or adequate procedures to evaluate the usability of these services [58].

At the same time, the music distribution industry has a great economic interest in the development of such platforms, and a huge technological advantage over academia in terms of the amounts of music and processing power they can use to build and deploy them. Therefore, many music discovery platforms have been developed by industry with attention to both algorithms and user experience, and with a clear focus and need for their industrial and commercial viability. These include Pandora, Spotify, Apple Music, Shazam, and many more.

2.4 Summary and Research Gaps

In this chapter we have introduced the concept of discovery from a broad background that draws from philosophy, cognition, design, and technology. We have identified the many

benefits of exploration and discovery, as well as the growing need for effective discovery tools in the digital age. Within music in particular, we have studied the various different ways of discovering music, and the many motivations for doing so. We have stated the need for means of accessing music that satisfy our exploratory needs, as well as principles for the design of such interfaces and specific examples of how they can be built. Finally, we have reviewed the most relevant approaches to music discovery according to four facets: level of user interaction, device, technology, and field of study. This review is summarized in Table 2.1.

The level of user interaction required and the target device naturally seem to go hand in hand, as explained in Section 2.3.2: mobile devices are better suited for platforms requiring less interaction, while active music exploration is better suited for full-screen desktop environments, with general-purpose platforms being present across all devices.

The technology used in the development of these platforms does not seem to be significantly correlated to any of the other dimensions we have studied, as a wide variety of technological approaches is present across the spectrum of music discovery platforms. However, in the development of interfaces for active music exploration we do see a frequent use of dimensionality reduction techniques to generate 2D or 3D spaces in which music catalogs can be browsed. These systems rely on either metadata or audio-based features to perform the dimensionality reduction, although metadata is often used nevertheless alongside audio-based algorithms to aid with navigation e.g. color-coding points by genre [20] or labeling regions with descriptive tags [36].

Table 2.1: Summary of the reviewed music discovery platforms.

Name / Author	Description	Level of interaction	Device	Technology used	Focus
Noxia MixRadio	Online music radio	Low	Mobile	Curated playlists	Industry
Pandora	Online music radio	Low	Cross-platform	Expert annotations	Industry
Spotify Discover Weekly, SoundCloud, Apple Music, Last.fm, Deezer, Google Play Music, Amazon Prime Music	Music recommendation	Medium	Cross-platform	Collaborative filtering, content-based recommendation, music similarity	Industry
iTunes Genius, Spotify Radio, Apple Music Radio, YouTube Related Mix	Playlist generation	Medium	Cross-platform	Collaborative filtering, music similarity	Industry
Pampalk, Schedl et al., Knees et al., Lillie, Stober, Soriano et al.	Active music exploration	High	Desktop	Dimensionality reduction	Academia (algorithm-centered)
Arhippainen et al., Lehtiniemi, Chen, Hoashi et al., Jentsch	Users and usability in music discovery	-	-	-	Academia (design-centered)

Finally, regarding the field from which these platforms have been proposed, it is worth noting that there is no significant contribution from industry to the field of active music exploration. All of the commercial music discovery platforms we have reviewed are focused on either low-interaction or general-purpose discovery, while all of the interfaces with more complex and experimental interaction models come from the academic world, focusing on either algorithms or usability. Why is there currently no widely used platform for active music discovery? Surely there is an audience for it, given the amount of research in the field. Why haven't any of the interfaces proposed by academia evolved into a successful platform with a large catalog and widespread use?

One possible answer to these questions lies in the relationship between the platform and its users. As pointed out by Arhippainen et al. [56] and Lehtiniemi [24], the quality of the experience provided by a music discovery platform greatly depends on factors such as its users' temporal and spacial context, listening habits, social and cultural background, musical taste, and musical training. Therefore, it is critical to the success of such a platform to understand its potential audience prior to its development, and to have the desired music browsing experience guide the technology and not the other way around.

However, as our review has shown, most of the academic contributions to music discovery come from research on either technology or user-centered design, but not both. Schedl et al. [59] analyze the lack of user-centric music information retrieval (MIR) research in general, identifying causes such as the lack of awareness of the limitations of system-centric evaluations, or the complexity and cost of user-centric evaluations. Lehtiniemi [24] notes that most evaluations of MIR systems, especially in music discovery, focus on evaluating algorithm performance rather than overall user experience. Nevertheless, valuable contributions have been made to bridge this gap: Cunningham et al. [60] recorded everyday encounters of a group of students with new music, developing their findings into design principles for MIR research. This is a clear example of the way the subjectivity and complexity of users' needs and behavior can actually be related to specific guidelines for the development of music technology.

In conclusion, we believe that the lack of user-centered design principles in music discovery research represents a great opportunity for further development—even more so in the

case of active music exploration, as the heavier interaction puts the user in a more central role. As we have seen, there is substantial literature on the technological engines that make such platforms possible, as well as on the design implications from the point of view of the user. By building on both these existing bodies of knowledge, and by experimenting from a user-centered perspective, we aim to identify an audience, context, and interaction model that result in an improved active music discovery experience.

Chapter 3

METHODOLOGY I: USER-CENTERED DESIGN

As stated in the Introduction, in this project we intend to answer the following question:

How can specific problems that users face when finding new music be solved through alternative ways of browsing music catalogs?

The following two chapters introduce the methodology we have followed in order to answer it. This chapter is concerned with answering the questions *what problem?* and *what users?*, while in Chapter 4 we answer the question *what new way of browsing music catalogs?*. The remainder of this chapter presents the motivation, design, results, and conclusions of a series of in-depth interviews with potential users that were carried out to better understand their habits and needs. The methodology presented in this chapter draws mainly from the user-centered design and prototyping handbook *Experimentation Manual: The Hands-On Guide To Experimentation-Driven Innovation* by Paju et al.

3.1 Survey Purpose

A key step in user-centered design (UCD) methodology is to gain first-hand knowledge of the habits and needs of potential users of the system we intend to develop. This ensures that we will be building something that is actually useful in real-world scenarios, helps us prioritize the development of certain features, and provides us with new perspectives and additional insights into the problem.

In this case, we are aiming to find a specific problem encountered by music listeners when finding new music that calls for a new means of browsing music catalogs. Therefore, the purpose of our survey is to link certain user traits with a certain music discovery problem. Arhippainen et al. [56] mention the following features as being relevant in the description and classification of music listeners:

- **Listening time and location:** the contexts in which users listen to music e.g. relaxing at home, making dinner, at work, commuting or driving...
- **Listening mode:** how attentively users listen to music, what activities they do while listening to music.
- **Listening frequency:** how often users listen to music.
- **Listening format:** what kind of medium users employ to listen to music e.g. CD, vinyl, low/high quality digital formats...
- **Musical preferences and vocabulary:** not only what kind of music users listen to, but also what criteria they use to describe their musical preferences e.g. genre, mood, countries, epochs...
- **Degree of control over what is played:** how strongly users decide beforehand what they will listen to, ranging from listening to whatever is on the radio to carefully picking a specific item from their personal collection.
- **Use of playlists:** the amount of playlists users have, how often they create them, and what they use them for.
- **Social components:** how users interact with friends online in their experience of music by using collaborative playlists or sharing music on social media.

3.2 Survey Design

A sample of the form used to carry out the survey is included in the Appendix. The forms were filled in by the interviewer, so as to give the participants more freedom to speak about

their habits and more comfort to carry out the exercises. The questions can be split into two groups according to their purpose, as explained in the previous section: the first aims to identify users' traits and habits, while the second aims to unveil the problems and unmet needs they face when finding new music.

3.2.1 Understanding users' traits and habits

Questions 1–4 cover basic identification and demographic aspects. Questions 5–7 are open-ended and cover the user's musical background, training and activity.

In the next block, a series of questions (8–26) aims at describing the type of music listener the participants are: describing their musical taste and quantifying the frequency with which they listen to music, both in general and in a variety of situations (in hours/day and hours/week, both for the week of the interview and average week), the strength of their musical choices, the popularity of the music they listen to, their focus on lyrics or instrumentals (all three in 1–7 Likert scales), and the media on which they consume music.

Finally, questions 27–34 provide insights into the interviewee's use of playlists, by quantifying how many playlists they have in offline and online music platforms, how often they create and reuse them, and how often they use certain special types of playlists such as curated, automatically generated or recommended, and collaborative playlists. Interviewees were asked for any additional comments at the end of each of these blocks.

3.2.2 Understanding users' problems and unmet needs

The second half of the interview consisted of two practical music discovery tasks using Spotify. This platform was chosen due to the size of its catalog and its position as the leader of the online music market in Europe [3], as well as for its active development of music discovery technology [21].

In a first exercise, participants were asked to create a new playlist with five songs they know and like. In a second exercise, they were asked to search the platform for five new songs that they like, that were previously unknown to them, and that they would like to listen to together with the songs they chose in the first exercise, and add them to the playlist. In both

exercises, participants were told to freely use any of the mechanisms the platform offers to find music, and to "think out loud" and explain how they felt so as to provide better insight into their experience and its problematic elements.

After the exercises, participants were asked (questions 36–45) to rate the similarity of the ten songs in their playlist according to different facets, namely instrumentation, rhythm, melody, harmony, lyrics, artists, genre, and mood; and how strongly they felt that the similarity criteria used in the platform's recommendations was aligned with their own criteria. Continuing on similarity, they were asked what musical facets they would like to use, and what kind of connections between songs/artists, if any, they like to discover, when finding new music.

In the next block (questions 46–56), they were asked about the aspects that made their music discovery experience easy, fun, difficult, boring, or frustrating, as well as how much they liked the new music they had found.

Next, they were asked (questions 57 and 58) two questions unrelated to music, aimed at finding potential metaphors of organization, exploration and discovery to be used in the proposed system: a significant discovery they had recently made and how they came across it, and how they organize and browse the largest collection they own, be it clothes, pictures or stamps, for example.

Finally, they were asked (questions 58–68) about their interest in some features that had already been brainstormed as ideas for the development of a solution: explanation and control over the way algorithmic recommendations are generated, and use of background information e.g. Wikipedia excerpts. Again, after each of these blocks users were asked for any additional comments.

3.3 Survey Results and Discussion

The interviews involved a total of 11 users, of which 4 were women and 7 were men, all of which were residents of Spain. Participants were friends, classmates, family or colleagues of the author. Ages ranged from 22 to 62, the mean and median ages being 31 and 24 respectively. 4 participants reported having no musical training, while 6 and 1 reported having some degree

and a high degree of musical training respectively. 4 participants reported regularly playing an instrument (with one of them regularly performing music live), while 7 reported not doing so. 8 of the 11 participants claimed to be familiar with Spotify, the platform used for the music discovery exercises. While the size of the sample prevents us from claiming any statistical generalizability of these results, the focus of this survey is qualitative rather than quantitative, as its aim is to obtain an in-depth understanding of each individual's experience and the problems they face.

3.3.1 Traits and habits

As one might expect, with a sample this size there was little correlation to be found between the different traits that were the topic of the first part of the survey: it is impossible to claim, for example, that musically trained people spend more time attentively listening to music than those who are not musically trained; that there is a relation between musical training and genre; or that people who like learning and analyzing lyrics create a lot of playlists.

When asked about the frequency with which they listen to music while doing certain activities, it was the case for all activities that a majority of users thought their behavior the week of the interview was representative of an average week. This points out that listening to music is a very steady habit: the frequency with which one listens to music changes little over time, even if it is very low.

Of the 11 participants, 10 stated they listen to music on online streaming platforms, with Spotify being first choice for all of them, and some mentioning YouTube as an alternative. 7 participants use CD's frequently, all of them mentioning their cars' sound systems as the main reason behind this. Streaming and compression quality were of little relevance to all of the participants except for those with a technical background.

Regarding the use of playlists, it is worth noting that only 2 of the 11 participants had more than 3 playlists in their personal offline music collections, while this was true for 7 participants in the case of online music platforms. This illustrates the shift of digital music towards on-demand streaming. Only one participant had ever used a collaborative playlist, while all of the others except for two had never even heard of them. 9 of the 11 participants

stated they regularly use automatically generated playlists, all of them mentioning Spotify Discover Weekly as a useful tool to find new music. Spotify radios and YouTube related mixes were also mentioned as frequent resources for music discovery.

3.3.2 Problems and unmet needs

Regarding the importance of different facets of music in perceived similarity, the survey shows that users do not have a clear-cut notion of music similarity. When asked an open-ended question about the reason why they thought the songs in their playlist were similar, users mostly used ill-defined terms such as sound, mood, and style. These terms are all the more ambiguous if we keep in mind that the interviewees did not (except for two of them) have any background in music technology. When asked to rate the importance of specific aspects of music in similarity using a 1–7 Likert scale, 8 out of 11 participants rated instrumentation, mood and genre 5 or above; while for rhythm and lyrics this was only true for 5 participants; 4 participants for melody; and 3 for harmony.

Four of the participants stated that the platform's understanding of similarity was somewhat aligned with their own criteria. When asked for new criteria they would like to use, participants mentioned cover art similarity, "polar opposites" (i.e. actually suggesting very dissimilar music), explicit geographical and temporary constraints, band members in common, and record labels. 8 of the 11 participants mentioned at least one type of connection between songs/artists they like to discover alongside the new music itself, mentioning cover versions, influences and collaborations between artists, artists' evolution through the years, artists that played in the same festival, songs that are featured in the same film or advertisement, and countries of origin.

9 out of 11 participants stated they liked the new music they found in the exercises (rated it 5 or above on a 1-7 Likert scale). However, only three stated it was easy to find new music, citing difficulties such as knowing most of the suggestions, a heavy bias in recommendations towards popularity, the use of genre and mood taxonomies that are either different to the users' understanding or lack granularity, and the lack of other relationships to explore besides artists, genres and moods.

4 of the 11 participants stated discovering music was fun, naming the visual design and discovery itself as fun elements, and the dryness of the list view, filtering through music they don't like, and excessive simplicity as boring elements.

7 participants mentioned frustrating elements including a bias towards popularity, the opacity or lack of explanations about recommendations, a metadata architecture that is not suitable for classical music, sudden mood changes with ads or auto-generated playlists, and the loading time of the user interface.

7 participants stated they were likely to further explore the artists they had discovered during the exercises, while only one participant said they were likely to share the new music they had found on social media.

Regarding non-musical collections, 5 of the 8 participants who could think of a large collection they owned mentioned photographs and images, which were sorted chronologically in three cases, by color in another, and by artist and theme in another. One participant mentioned a collection of over 50 party sunglasses which were sorted by color, because she decides the color first of all depending on the rest of her outfit, and by the shape of the glass within each color. Similarly, another participant mentioned his collection of pants was sorted first by context (sport versus formal) because it is a criteria he has already decided when opening the closet, and by color within each context. Another participant mentioned a collection of about 100 postcards that were sorted by country, while another one mentioned a collection of seashells that are placed around her room roughly according to the distance between the beaches where she found them. In summary, users' collections are sorted by color, geographical distribution, or the order in which they are created (e.g. chronologically ordering photos) or used (e.g. pants by context or sunglasses by matching outfit).

The reported non-musical discoveries were extremely wide-ranging: from biblical characters found on TV, and films recommended by friends; to a reflection on the way sacred spaces are created, sparked by intrusive voices on an airplane; and new breathing techniques for flute players found through systematic trial and error.

Finally, regarding the proposed new features, 9 participants out of 11 said they would like it if music discovery platforms offered explanations of the way algorithmic recommendations are generated, while 8 of them said they wouldn't mind if the explanations were not provided.

The same numbers are true for the ability to interact with the way recommendations are generated. In the case of additional background information, 10 participants would like for platforms to have the feature, although 6 of them wouldn't mind if it weren't present.

3.4 Survey Conclusions

After describing the frustrating and boring aspects of the platform mentioned above, many participants went on to express a desire for more information about the songs that had been recommended and higher control over the discovery engine. As we have seen, 9 of the 11 participants reported at least one type of connection between songs or artists as something they like to discover while browsing music.

These needs were loosely related to certain groups of users determined by the traits and habits that were identified in the first part of the interview. Specifically, attentive listeners (participants who reported listening to music attentively at least one hour per week), loose-choosers (participants who reported choosing what they listen to beforehand as 1–3 on a 1–7 Likert scale), and multi-criteria browsers (participants who described their musical preferences using at least two different criteria).

88% of active listeners reported they like discovering connections between songs or artists, while the proportion was 50% for non-active listeners and 82% for all participants. Regarding the strength of musical choice, 100% of the loose-choosers like discovering connections, while this is true for only 75% of hard-choosers, and 82% of all participants. Finally, 100% of the multi-criteria browsers like discovering connections, compared to 71% of single-criteria browsers and 82% of all participants. Again, although the size of the sample prevents us from claiming any statistical generalizability of these results, a qualitative analysis of the explanations provided by the participants seems to support the idea that there is a certain user profile that has an unmet need for more information about the way different songs and artists are related. As active searchers for both new music and information about it, it is reasonable to think they are more prone than the average user to attentive listening and unplanned exploration, and are able to describe music in various ways.

In this chapter we intended to answer the questions *what problem?* and *what users?*. As a result of these in-depth interviews with potential users of our system, we have decided to focus on the problem of the lack of explicit connections between songs or artists, which as we have seen is loosely related to certain types of music listener: attentive listeners, loose-choosers, and multi-criteria browsers.

Chapter 4

METHODOLOGY II: ARIADNE

This chapter introduces Ariadne, the platform for music discovery that we have developed as the result of this project. It is structured as follows: Section 4.1 introduces the main idea behind Ariadne; Section 4.2 details the specifications for its development; Section 4.3 presents examples of its behavior; and Section 4.4 provides some final details on its implementation.

4.1 Concept

In the previous chapter, we saw that a common limitation of existing platforms for music discovery for a certain type of user stems from the black box-like nature of music recommendation engines. This prevents users from understanding how new music is related to music they already know, which is an essential cue in guessing whether they will like it or not; and obscures explicit control over the kind of music that is encountered.

However, simply adding text snippets next to elements in a list of songs to describe how they are related to other elements is not a good enough solution to this problem: it would quickly lead to even more on-screen information overload. At the same time, as we saw in Chapter 2, there is a need in music discovery in general for new and more explorable means of accessing and displaying music catalogs that go beyond simple text-based searches and lists of results.

Ariadne was conceived with the idea to turn precisely what existing platforms lack – explicit and meaningful connections between new and known songs that help us *locate* them in the space of our music experience – into the main theme of a new way of interacting with a music catalog. In our platform, we explore a music collection by jumping between songs using semantically explicit connections, such as the ones proposed by participants in the survey presented in the previous chapter: a song by a band with a member in common with the band that wrote the current song, by a band that played in the same festival, a song featured in the soundtrack of the same film...

In the Greek myth of Theseus and the Minotaur¹, Theseus promises to slay the Minotaur, a half-man, half-bull monster that lives in a labyrinth in the island of Crete, and to which the cretans must pay a yearly tax in the form of young women. Ariadne, the daughter of Minos, king of Crete, falls in love with him and, to ensure his safe return, gives him a ball of thread that he uses to find his way back through the labyrinth after defeating the beast.

In our labyrinth there are no beasts to be found, only music. However, there is a great risk of getting lost: even if we only allowed jumping between two songs that were written by bands with a member in common (a type of link for which one would assume a certain stylistic consistency), one could start at a song by Compay Segundo and arrive at Iron Maiden with only 11 steps². Links with looser musical ties such as film soundtracks or music festivals could quickly lead to a very chaotic exploration. This is where Ariadne will help us: thanks to her thread, we can retrace our steps at any time and continue exploring the labyrinth from a better-known place.

4.2 Specifications

The following specifications describe the general behavior of Ariadne:

- **Canvas:** The exploration takes place in a 2D plane that starts out as an empty, black rectangle.

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Theseus#The_myth_of_Theseus_and_the_Minotaur

²http://static.echonest.com/SixDegreesOfBlackSabbath/?src_id=2594&dest_id=10042

- **Knots:** A knot is a point in the music exploration. It represents a song and how it is connected to other songs in the exploration. Knots are represented as circles in the canvas.
- **Threads:** A thread is a connection between two knots. Different thread types are available: songs by the same artist, songs by a band with a member in common, songs by a band that played in the same festival... Threads are represented as lines connecting knots in the canvas.
- **Initialization:** The user can type in a song to begin the exploration, or let the system provide a random starting point. The song is placed as a knot in the center of the canvas.
- **Thread generation:** Clicking on a knot causes new threads to appear leading out of it. New threads can point either to new knots, which are automatically placed so that the map grows in the direction of empty space; or towards already existing knots, causing the existing map to be more densely connected.
- **Perspective and the ambiguity of similarity:** The x and y dimensions of the 2D plane have no meaning. Absolute position and direction therefore have no meaning either. However, as new knots are placed close to their parent knot, knots that are close together are expected to be similar. The user can move any amount of knots at any time so as to rearrange their spatial distribution in order to better reflect the user's personal understanding of music, highlight connections to a certain knot, or simply clear some space to continue extending the map.
- **Orientation:** The automatic placement of knots only affects the new knots generated with new threads. Once a knot is placed, either automatically or by the user, only the user can change its position. This is done to give the map a constant geometric shape so that the user can get familiar with it.
- **Overview:** After thread generation, the viewpoint is panned so that the parent knot of the new threads is centered, and zoomed so that all of the new threads are visible.

The user can zoom in and out and pan at any moment to get a holistic overview of the structure of the map.

- **Relevance:** The user can delete irrelevant knots by right-clicking them.
- **Navigation:** Threads are color coded according to their type. Knots are filled with album artwork.
- **Explorability:** No text is displayed on screen by default. The user must hover the mouse over knots and threads to view information about them in a small tooltip. This encourages the user to engage with the platform.
- **Local highlighting:** While hovering over a knot, its threads and neighboring knots are highlighted, while all other elements are obscured, so as to instantly give the user information about its function in the map and its connectedness.

4.3 Examples of use

The following screenshots depict the behavior of Ariadne when using *Californication*, by the Red Hot Chili Peppers, as starting point. A full video of this exploration session can be found on YouTube³.

Figure 4.1: Initial state of Ariadne. The starting song (*Californication*) is shown in the center of the canvas, and four new knots (songs) have appeared, connected to the original knot by threads of different types.

³<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=P7HNjnVrBHQ>

Figure 4.2: Detail of a highlighted thread. This yellow thread indicates a connection between a song by the Red Hot Chili Peppers and a song by their former member Dave Navarro.

Figure 4.3: Further thread generation. After clicking on one of the four initial knots, new threads are found and connected to it, extending the map downwards.

Figure 4.4: Ariadne map after some exploration. Linear exploration downwards from the starting point *Californication*, at the center of the cross in the top left, eventually led to a closed loop through the song immediately above the starting point. A tree-like structure is visible to the right.

Figure 4.5: Highlighting a knot. Hovering over a knot highlights its connected threads and neighboring knots, which helps us quickly place it in relation to the rest of the map.

4.4 Implementation details

Ariadne is open-source⁴ and easily extendable to feature new thread types. It currently offers the following thread types: song by the same artist; song by a band with a member in common; song by a band member; song by an artist that played in the same festival. These thread types were chosen from the list of connections mentioned by users due to their ease of implementation given the architecture of the chosen database.

Its backend is written in Python, while the frontend runs on a standard web browser and is written in JavaScript, using the CytoscapeJS library [61]. It exposes the entire MusicBrainz⁵ database, which was chosen for its considerable size (around 17 million recordings), and its rich and structured information about artists, recordings and their relationships. The ability to work with a local copy of the database rather than querying an online service also makes MusicBrainz a good solution in terms of speed and reliability.

Ariadne's main limitation is currently its inability to stream music, a fundamental one. This is due to the the fact that MusicBrainz is more of a music encyclopedia than a music catalog, as it does not host audio but only metadata. There was a trade-off between a vast amount of structured metadata and the inability to play music, which was otherwise difficult to implement anyway due to copyright issues.

⁴<https://www.github.com/danielbalcells/ariadne>

⁵<https://www.musicbrainz.org>

Chapter 5

CONCLUSIONS

Summary

In this work, we have taken on the challenge of improving the way we access and discover music in digital catalogs. We began by rooting our research in wide grounds by drawing from well-established bodies of knowledge in the fields of music information retrieval, design, musicology, and cognition. Our review of existing approaches revealed that there was an opportunity to make a valuable contribution by following a user-centered design methodology to develop an innovative way of accessing and exploring music catalogs. In-depth interviews with potential users pointed out that existing platforms for music discovery hide both information about new music and control over the discovery engine behind black box-like algorithms. We turned this drawback into the central theme of Ariadne, a new interface for music discovery that uses semantically explicit connections between songs to allow the user to build and shape their own constellation-like maps.

Discussion

This project started with the aim to develop a new way to discover music based on the habits and problems experienced by real-world music listeners. Its main outcome, Ariadne, is exactly this: a novel means for the access and exploration of large music catalogs that was conceived by connecting the dots of individual comments and thoughts that real users gave us. From this point of view, it is safe to say that the main goal of the project has been achieved.

Time constraints imposed a choice between the full implementation of a prototype and an evaluation that would have been based on mock-ups of the Ariadne concept. We preferred to end the project with a concrete working solution, for which informal feedback has been very positive, and that quickly sparked ideas for additional features when shown to various audiences. However, an objective measure of the degree to which this new tool correctly solves the problems it addresses and improves users' music discovery experience remains unknown.

Future work

The interface presented in Chapter 4 is a prototype, and as such it must be improved in order to deliver a complete and enjoyable music discovery experience. The first and most important task to be carried out next is an evaluation that can characterize its behavior in objective terms as well as its potential from the point of view of real users. At the same time, new features to be added include:

- Fuzzy search of starting point by song title. Currently, the user must input the MusicBrainz ID of the desired song.
- User selection of thread types to make the map grow only according to the desired criteria.
- Music player, as MusicBrainz hosts a large catalog of metadata but not the audio for the songs.
- More thread types (only 4 are currently implemented): cover versions, influences between bands, geographical relationships, presence in cinema/TV, audio-based measures...
- Faster querying and smarter ranking to determine which of all possible threads of a given type is finally displayed. The current solution defaults to a random choice from the first 10 threads returned by the database.
- Various visualization presets and smarter/customized layouts.

- Ability to export an exploration session as an image or data file to share it with friends.
- Minor fixes to the network infrastructure and client-server model.

Lessons learned

As the final project of a Master's degree, my expectations for this project were not only to carry it out successfully, but also to learn with it. I'm happy to say this has been the case.

At a technological level, this is my first experience building a software application of considerable size and complexity on my own, encompassing both a server-side back-end and a client-side front-end. Specific technologies I've used for the first time include SQL databases and their access from Python code; front-end development in JavaScript; and client-server communication between different programming languages using JSON.

This has led me to note that more time should be allocated for implementation when using many technologies for the first time. This is one of the main causes behind the delays in the project that caused us to drop the evaluation.

The first thorough review of existing work and the second search for a broader context for the project (although presented in opposite order in the document) were humbling and a useful lesson in patience. Good ideas are more likely to pop up from an abundance of other ideas.

Finally, from a methodological perspective, this project is a valuable lesson in listening to real people and taking their perspectives into account as a key part of the project. If the uncertainty that this open planning creates is handled correctly, people's ideas can save a lot of work.

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Appendix:
Survey used in the user studies

Music Browsing: needfinding

*Required

1. **E-mail ***

2. **Age ***

Mark only one oval.

- <14
- 14-18
- 18-25
- 25-35
- 35-45
- 45-55
- 55-65
- 65+

3. **Gender ***

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

4. **Occupation ***

5. **Do you play music? ***

6. **What level of formal music training do you have? ***

7. **Are you a live performer? If so, how often do you perform? ***

Music consumption habits: how do you listen to music?

8. How much do you listen to music? *

How many hours did you spend listening to music yesterday? And last weekend?

9. Musical taste *

Briefly describe what kind of music you like

10. Choosing what to listen to *

How strongly do you decide beforehand what you will listen to?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Whatever is on the radio /
my friends share on social
media / is playing at work or
the gym

I only
play
music
from my
curated
personal
collection

Out of the past seven days, how many days did you listen to music...

11. Attentively, focusing carefully on the music?

12. Is this also true for an average week?

13. At home, while browsing the web?

14. Is this also true for an average week?

15. While on the move (driving, commuting, biking, skating, walking)?

16. Is this also true for an average week?

17. While working?

18. Is this also true for an average week?

19. At clubs, bars, or socially drinking?

20. Is this also true for an average week?

21. When else did you listen to music last week?

22. Where else did you listen to music last week?

23. Music formats

Check all of the formats in which you usually listen to music

Tick all that apply.

- Online streaming - low quality
- Online streaming - high quality (YouTube HD, Spotify Premium 320kbps, etc)
- Low quality digital formats (mp3)
- High quality digital formats (WAV, FLAC)
- CD
- Hi-Fi CD
- Hi-Fi Vinyl

24. Not-popular vs Popular

How popular is the music you listen to?
Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

I mainly listen to unknown artists: they are never played on the radio or shops, if you asked someone on the street they wouldn't know them, etc

My favorite artists are everywhere: they are played on the radio, mass media write about them, most people on the street would recognize their name or face, etc

25. Lyrics vs Instruments

Do you pay more attention to the lyrics or to the instrumentation of a song?
Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Lyrics: I learn/understand/analyze/relate to them. Most of the music I like has vocals, and the lyrics are in a language I understand

Instrumental: I enjoy listening to the different instrumental sections and their interplay; vocals are just another instrument

26. Additional comments

How do you use playlists?

27. How many playlists do you have in your personal music collection?

28. How many playlists do you have in online music platforms?

29. How many playlists have you created in the past two weeks?

30. How many playlists created by other users have you used in the past two weeks?

31. How many automatically recommended playlists have you used in the past two weeks?

32. How many collaborative playlists have you used in the past two weeks?

33. How often do you reuse playlists?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

I create a playlist on the fly with the music I want to listen to now and never use it again

I listen to music through a set of playlists and edit them as I find new music

34. Additional comments

Task 1: finding music you know

Using the provided music platform, create a playlist with five songs you like that you would listen to as part of a playlist.

You can use any of the tools offered by the platform. Please think out loud and explain how you feel as you do so.

35. Are you familiar with this platform?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

47. How easy was it to find music that is both new to you and similar to other music you know?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Very hard. Most of the music I found was not similar at all to my playlist.

Very easy. Most of the songs I found were really similar to my playlist.

48. What difficulties have you encountered in your search?

49. How fun was it to find music that is both new to you and similar to other music you know?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Dull. Boring. I wanted to give up after a while.

It was really fun. I wanted to keep on looking for more new music when I was done.

50. What aspects made it fun or boring?

51. What elements of this platform frustrated you?

52. How likely are you to further explore the new artists you've found?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

I wouldn't listen to any more music by these artists

I'll start browsing their discography as soon as I can

53. How likely are you to recommend this new music to a friend or share it on social media?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

I won't tell anyone about it

I just tweeted it ten seconds ago

54. How aligned is this platform's understanding of music similarity with the criteria you would like to use to find new music?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Totally unaligned: it suggested music based on criteria that are irrelevant to me

Completely aligned: it suggested music based on the exact same criteria I would use

55. What aspects of similarity would you like to use to improve your experience when finding new music?

56. What kind of connections between songs/artists, if any, do you like to find when using music discovery services?

A few final questions

57. **What is the largest collection (photos, music, books, jewels, pencils, stamps) you own?
How do you organize and browse it?**

58. **What is the last significant discovery (a fact, a place, a personality, a film, food) you made?
How did you come across it?**

59. **What elements of music services usually frustrate you? What workarounds do you use to solve them?**

60. **If a music recommendation service featured explanations of the way the recommendation was generated, how would you feel?**

Mark only one oval.

- I like it
- I expect it
- I am neutral
- I can tolerate it
- I dislike it

61. **If a music recommendation service didn't feature explanations of the way the recommendation was generated, how would you feel?**

Mark only one oval.

- I like it
- I expect it
- I am neutral
- I can tolerate it
- I dislike it

62. In a music recommendation service, how important to you are explanations of the way recommendations are generated?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Not at all important	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely important						

63. If a music recommendation service featured the ability to interact with the way recommendations are generated (e.g. correcting it, changing its understanding of similarity, etc), how would you feel?

Mark only one oval.

- I like it
- I expect it
- I am neutral
- I can tolerate it
- I dislike it

64. If a music recommendation service didn't feature the ability to interact with the way recommendations are generated (e.g. correcting it, changing its understanding of similarity, etc), how would you feel?

Mark only one oval.

- I like it
- I expect it
- I am neutral
- I can tolerate it
- I dislike it

65. In a music recommendation service, how important to you is ability to interact with the way recommendations are generated (e.g. correcting it, changing its understanding of similarity, etc)?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Not at all important	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely important						

66. If a music service featured background information about artists (e.g. a Wikipedia excerpt), how would you feel?

Mark only one oval.

- I like it
- I expect it
- I am neutral
- I can tolerate it
- I dislike it

67. If a music service didn't feature background information about artists (e.g. a Wikipedia excerpt), how would you feel?

Mark only one oval.

- I like it
- I expect it
- I am neutral
- I can tolerate it
- I dislike it

68. In a music service, how important to you is background information about artists?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Not at all important	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely important						

Thanks a lot for your time!
